

Exchange Rate Pass-Through Effect and Inflation Dynamics in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This paper examined the exchange rate pass-through effect on inflation in Nigeria using quarterly data from 1995Q1 to 2023Q4. The data was analyzed using the fully modified ordinary least squares (FMOLS) and the vector autoregression (VAR) with accompanying impulse response function. The VAR model incorporated two lags with exchange rate, import prices, crude oil price, and real output growth being the variables within the system. Findings from the FMOLS technique of estimation indicated that both exchange rate and import prices exerted positive and significant effect on the consumer price index in Nigeria. This implies that both exchange rate and import prices are key drivers of inflationary pressure within the Nigerian economy. However, crude oil prices exerted a negative and significant effect on the consumer price index in Nigeria. The VAR model revealed that the exchange rate passes through the import prices to affect domestic prices in Nigeria. The impulse response functions indicated that the domestic prices responded positively to shocks in the import prices but negatively to shocks in crude oil prices. The domestic prices responded positively to shocks in exchange rate up to the sixth period after which the response became negative afterwards. The paper recommended that the Federal Government of Nigeria in conjunction with the National Planning Commission should prioritize structural reforms through the strategic implementation of import substitution policies.

Keywords: exchange rate, inflation, producer price index, consumer price index, VAR.

1. INTRODUCTION

The impact of exchange rate fluctuations on inflation and economic activity has been one of the major challenges to managing economic policy globally, and especially in emerging and developing nations. Exchange rate fluctuations are thought to impact a nation's economic competitiveness and cause internal economic distortions. The detrimental impacts of exchange rate fluctuation are widely known in the literature, and policymakers frequently hesitate to modify exchange rates because they believe it would have a negative impact on the economy, mostly through pass-through effects. The significance of the exchange rate as a practical instrument for attaining overall economic advancement has also been emphasized in the literature. This is predicated on the relationship between the exchange rate and other economic

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factors as well as the exchange rate's pivotal role in the formulation of monetary policy, as it is a vital component of the signalling channel via which policy choices are sent in order to accomplish the intended macroeconomic goals (Bada et al., 2016). Because central banks are tasked with controlling exchange rates and maintaining price stability, a thorough understanding of exchange rate pass-through is crucial for formulating policies.

Exchange rate pass-through (ERPT) is the percentage change in local currency import prices which occurs when the exchange rate between the exporting and importing economies changes by 1% (Goldberg and Knetter, 1997). The ERPT is typically used to describe how changes in exchange rates affect consumer pricing, import and export prices, trade volumes, and investments (Frimpong and Adam, 2010). The impact of exchange rate fluctuations on domestic prices and the rate of its transition defines their importance in macroeconomic adjustment. A high degree of pass-through means that changes in the exchange rate will alter the relative pricing of commodities, which will cause trade balances to quickly adjust. A high ERPT degree, for instance, makes imported goods more expensive, reduces demand for imports, and causes consumers to switch to domestically produced goods. Conversely, a low ERPT degree has little effect on domestic prices and trade balances.

Exchange rate regimes are crucial to ERPT; in a fixed exchange rate regime, economic agents quickly adjust prices because they believe that any change in the exchange rate is permanent, whereas in a flexible exchange rate regime, they do not quickly adjust their prices because they believe that changes are temporary. Economic agents in high-income nations do not quickly alter prices in reaction to fluctuations in the exchange rate because they limit enterprises' pricing power by fostering greater levels of domestic market competition. However, in low-income nations, the opposite is true (Razafimahefa, 2012). While expansionary monetary policy is linked to high ERPT because economic agents see it as unstable and tend to quickly adjust prices, contractionary monetary policy reduces the degree of ERPT.

Similarly, expansionary fiscal policy will increase the degree of pass-through because economic agents believe that the government will increase taxes or cut spending to address the accumulated fiscal deficit, which will inevitably lower firm profitability or contract the market. Conversely, contractionary fiscal policy will lessen the amount of pass-through due to the reduced level of fiscal deficit that is associated with. Overall, minimal pass-through is linked to sound macroeconomic policies which is an indication that policy effectiveness aids the effective management of the exchange rate as not to trigger inflationary tendencies within an economy.

Prices of imported consumption items, locally produced goods which inputs are priced in foreign currency, and prices of imported intermediate goods are the three main ways that changes in exchange rates affect consumer prices. In the first two channels (which are prices of imported consumption items and prices of locally produced goods which inputs prices are in foreign currency), changes in the exchange rate have a direct impact. This is because

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exchange rate depreciation will cause the prices of such goods to increase which therefore trigger a domestic rise in the prices of such goods in the economy. There are two steps in the pass-through procedure. Changes in the exchange rate are passed on to import prices at the first step. Changes in import prices are passed on to consumer prices in the second stage. For the last channel, changes in exchange rates have an indirect impact on local pricing by altering manufacturing costs (Sahminan, 2002). According to Lafleche (1996) and later affirmed by Hyde and Shah (2004), there are two main ways that changes in the exchange rate might impact domestic prices: directly and indirectly.

According to this line of reasoning, changes in the prices of imported inputs (such as raw materials and capital goods) and finished commodities can have a direct impact on local pricing. The domestic price of imported finished goods decreases when the value of the domestic currency increases. Similarly, consumers are more inclined to pay higher import costs when the value of the home currency declines. Additionally, currency depreciation raises the cost of imported inputs, which might raise local enterprises' marginal cost of production. As a result, domestically made items become more expensive. However, it is stated that the indirect route happens when the native country's currency rate declines (Abdulahi, 2023). Because local items are less expensive than those made abroad, they are more affordable for overseas consumers. This will lead to an increase in aggregate demand and the amount of the demand for exports, which would raise domestic prices.

Evidence of incomplete ERPT and significant country-specific variations have been identified in empirical literature for both developed and developing economies, which naturally raises the question of what the fundamental factors influencing pass-through are (Ca' Zorzi et al., 2007). Taylor (2000) proposes that prices' response to changes in the exchange rate is positively correlated with inflation. Evidence from many investigations seems to support the Taylor theory. It seems that developing markets have a stronger positive correlation between inflation and the degree of pass-through (Choudhri and Hakura, 2006). Prior research on ERPT in Nigeria used a variety of approaches, including unconstrained error correction method (UECM), vector autoregression (VAR), Granger causality tests, and the correlation and vector error correction framework. By incorporating crude oil price to the modelling framework and extending the research period with quarterly data to incorporate higher frequencies, this study uses the vector autoregression (VAR) to investigate exchange rate pass-through to inflation in Nigeria from the first quarter of 1995 to the fourth quarter of 2023.

The paper which is presented in five sections has section 1 being the introduction followed by literature review in section 2. In section three, the methodology of the research is presented while section 4 captures the empirical findings. Lastly, section 5 presents the conclusion and recommendations from the study.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

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2.1 Conceptual Literature

2.1.1. Exchange Rate Pass-Through (ERPT)

The exchange rate pass-through (ERPT) describes how changes in exchange rates affect consumer pricing, import and export prices, trade volumes, and investments (Frimpong and Adam, 2010). It is measured as the percentage change in local currency import prices which occurs when the exchange rate between the exporting and importing economies changes by a unit percentage point (Goldberg and Knetter, 1997). Precisely, exchange rate pass-through is the elasticity of local currency import prices with respect to the local currency price of foreign currency. Thus, it is given as the ratio of import prices to changes in exchange rate of importing countries. According to Goldberg and Knetter (1997), it is sometimes expressed as the percentage change in import prices in the local currency that results from a one percent change in the exchange rate between the importing and exporting nations. Retail and consumer pricing are impacted when import costs fluctuate. Exchange rate pass-through (ERPT) can also be referred to the extent to which changes in the exchange rate affect domestic prices. It measures how fluctuations in a country's currency value influence the prices of imported and domestically produced goods. ERPT can be classified into two types: Complete Pass-Through is when a 1% change in the exchange rate leads to a 1% change in domestic prices. While, an Incomplete Pass-Through is when a 1% currency depreciation or change in the exchange rate leads to less than a 1% rise or changes in domestic prices.

The degree of ERPT depends on various factors, including the openness of an economy, monetary policy credibility, inflation expectations, and market structures. Studies suggest that ERPT is generally higher in developing economies due to their reliance on imports and weak monetary policy frameworks, whereas in advanced economies, strong central bank credibility and inflation-targeting regimes tend to reduce ERPT.

A high degree of pass-through means that changes in the exchange rate will alter the relative pricing of commodities, which will cause trade balances to quickly adjust. A high ERPT degree, for instance, makes imported goods more expensive, reduces demand for imports, and causes consumers to switch to domestically produced goods. Conversely, a low ERPT degree has little effect on domestic prices and trade balances. There is a larger transmission of inflation between nations when exchange-rate pass-through is higher (Campa and Goldberg, 2005). Therefore, the law of one price and purchasing power parity are linked to exchange-rate pass-through.

2.1.2. Producer Price Index (PPI)

The Producer Price Index (PPI) measures the average change over time in the prices paid to United State producers of goods and services. It serves as an indicator of inflationary pressures at the production level before they are passed on to consumers. The Producer Price

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Index is crucial in analyzing cost-push inflation, as increases in producer prices may lead to higher consumer prices if firms pass higher costs onto consumers. However, the extent of this transmission depends on market conditions, pricing power, and demand elasticity. Producers Price Index is also linked to exchange rate movements, as currency depreciation can increase the cost of imported raw materials, leading to higher producer prices and potential inflationary pressures.

2.1.3. Consumer Price Index (CPI)

The Consumer Price Index (CPI) measures the average change in prices paid by consumers for a basket of goods and services over time. It is the most widely used measure of inflation and serves as a key economic indicator for policymakers, businesses, and consumers. CPI is categorized into:

- (a) **Headline CPI:** Includes all goods and services, including volatile components like food and energy.
- (b) **Core CPI:** Excludes food and energy to provide a clearer picture of underlying inflation trends.

Exchange rate fluctuations affect CPI through the import price channel, where depreciation increases the cost of imported goods, directly raising consumer prices. However, the extent of CPI changes depends on firms' pricing strategies, competition, and monetary policy responses.

2.1.4. Inflation and Its Linkages

Inflation refers to the persistent increase in the general price level of goods and services in an economy over time (Phillips, 1958). Inflation can erode the purchasing power of consumers, distort price signals, and reduce the standard of living.

It can be classified into:

- (a) **Demand-Pull Inflation:** Caused by rising demand outpacing supply.
- (b) **Cost-Push Inflation:** Resulting from increased production costs, including higher wages and import prices.
- (c) **Imported Inflation:** Stemming from currency depreciation leading to higher prices for imported goods.

The relationship between exchange rates, Producers Price Index, Consumer Price Index, and Inflation is dynamic. A depreciation of the currency raises import costs, increasing Producers Price Index, which may then pass through to Consumers Price Index, leading to higher inflation. However, central bank policies, wage dynamics, and market competition play critical roles in determining the extent of this transmission.

Understanding the interactions between exchange rate pass-through, PPI, CPI, and inflation is crucial for economic policy formulation. Policymakers must consider these linkages

when designing exchange rate policies, inflation-targeting strategies, and price stabilization mechanisms to ensure economic stability.

2.2 Theoretical Literature

The theoretical underpinnings for this study hinges on the law of one price (LOOP), the purchasing power parity (PPP), and the monetary approach to exchange rate determination.

2.2.1 Law of One Price and Purchasing Power Parity

With the assumptions that there are no trade restrictions or transportation cost, the theory of purchasing power parity (PPP), further developed from the law of one price (LOOP), provides the theoretical basis for the link between prices and exchange rates. Nevertheless, trade barriers occur in real-world scenarios, which skew the fundamental assumptions of PPP. The law of one price is still helpful in comprehending how prices and exchange rates are related, despite the weak assumption of absence of trade barriers. This relationship between the domestic price and exchange rate is derived from the LOOP, which stipulates that identical goods sold in different countries must sell for the same price when prices are expressed in a common currency, provided that trade barriers are removed and there is free competition and price flexibility. As a result, when two markets are in equilibrium, the prices of tradable items should not fluctuate when represented in the same currency, ensuring a full pass-through. Therefore, even if the marketplaces are in two different nations, a change in the native currency in one market would result in an identical change in the pricing in the other market (Bada et al., 2016). The PPP without any transportation costs or tariffs can be expressed algebraically as follows:

$$P_t^d = EXCR_t P_t^f \quad (1)$$

Equation (1) states that the domestic price at time t (P_t^d) is equal to the product of the nominal exchange rate at time t ($EXCR_t$) and the world import prices (P_t^f).

However, in some cases, the law of one price might or might not hold due to trade restrictions. This is predicated on the reality that a variety of factors impact domestic import prices, including manufacturing costs, producer mark-ups, and fluctuations in exchange rates. The principle of PPP is the macroeconomic counterpart to the law of one price. While the law of one price links exchange rates to the relative prices of an individual commodity, the purchasing power parity relates exchange rates to the relative prices of a basket of goods. Depending on whether the focus is on the macroeconomic or company level, both theories are utilized as the theoretical foundation for exchange rate pass-through. However, transaction costs, non-traded items, price stickiness, imperfect competition, and some regulatory barriers make purchasing power parity unsustainable in the short term (Feenstra and Taylor, 2008).

2.2.2 Monetary Approach to Exchange Rate Determination

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The monetary theory explains how changes in exchange rates will directly impact price levels by combining Krugman's (1986) monetary exchange rate model with the law of one price and the purchasing power parity. According to the monetary approach to prices and exchange rates, an increase in the money supply growth rate should, under all other circumstances, be equivalent to an increase in the rates of inflation and exchange rate depreciation. The method demonstrates the long-term interdependence of all nominal variables, including the money supply, interest rate, price level, and exchange rate. Therefore, decisions on monetary policy have the power to significantly impact several significant economic outcomes, most notably inflation and pricing.

2.3 Empirical Literature

Some studies have been conducted to ascertain the exchange rate pass-through (ERPT) effect across different economies. McCarthy (2000) discovered that in some developed economies, the pass-through of exchange rates to consumer prices was quite low. According to the study, the rate of pass-through has a negative link with exchange rate volatility and a positive link with trade openness. However, Gagnon and Ihrig (2001) were unable to identify a consistent link between ERPT and the monetary behaviour of the developed nations under study. The effect of exchange rate swings on import and consumer prices in Japan, Singapore, Korea, and Thailand was assessed by Kang and Wang (2003). The authors discovered that during the post-crisis era (1998–2001), exchange rate fluctuations had a greater impact on import and consumer prices than they did during the pre-crisis period (1991–1996).

For each of the 18 goods they examined, Hoque and Razzaque (2004) demonstrated different pass-through impacts on Bangladeshi export prices. With the exception of the nation's main export, ready-made clothing, which was determined to be insensitive to fluctuations in the exchange rate, it likewise demonstrated full pass-through effects for all of its main export items. The study also showed that, depending on the commodity's demand pattern in different export markets, export prices exhibited unique pass-through behaviour. Evidence of short-term partial pass-through in 23 OECD nations was shown by Campa and Goldberg (2005). According to the study, import prices in local currencies represented around 46% of short-term and 65% of long-term changes in exchange rates. For several of the selected nations, total pass-through was refuted even if individual pass-through elasticities were determined to be closer to 1. Since the pass-through into import prices was lower in nations with low average inflation and little exchange rate fluctuation, the authors also discovered that macroeconomic factors have a substantial but limited role in explaining cross-country variations in pass-through elasticities.

McCarthy (2007) shows that ERPT has decreased in sub-Saharan African (SSA) economies during the mid-1990s. Additionally, the discovered that the mid-1990s saw the most noticeable and statistically significant change in the nominal effective exchange rate variable's coefficient. All model specifications showed a significant drop in elasticities. It was predicted

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that pass-through elasticities were reduced by around 50%. When Ghosh and Rajan (2007) calculated the ERPT's impact on consumer prices in India, they discovered a long-term pass-through elasticity of 40% and a short-term one of 10%. Additionally, they demonstrated evidence of a larger pass-through in the post-liberalization era, which they ascribed to increased economic openness.

Aliyu et al. (2008) used quarterly data from 1986 to 2007 to investigate the extent of ERPT to import and consumer prices in Nigeria. Despite the fact that import costs were greater than consumer prices during that time, the study demonstrated that ERPT was considerable in Nigeria. According to their findings, a one percent exchange rate shock had pass-through effects on import and consumer prices of 14.3% and 10.5%, respectively, four quarters in advance. The conservative view in the literature that ERPT is always significantly greater in developing nations than in industrialized economies is somewhat refuted by their suggestion that ERPT in Nigeria decreases down the pricing chain. According to Shintani et al. (2009), decreased inflation was linked to the US ERPT's reductions in the 1980s and 1990s. In a related study, Ghosh and Rajan (2009) discovered that in every situation, Thailand's ERPT to inflation was greater than Korea's. Additionally, they demonstrated that ERPT was higher for import costs than for consumer prices in both nations, which further suggests that pass-through decreases occur along the pricing chain.

In a similar vein, Sahaa and Zhanga (2011) calculated the pass-through to CPI and verified that the ERPT to import prices was complete. Using a structural VAR model, their results showed that exchange rates had less of an impact on China's and India's growing domestic prices. Adelowokan (2012) used yearly data from 1970 to 2010, and the ordinary least squares estimate approach to examine the interest and inflation rate channels of ERPT in Nigeria. Since neither the Naira's lagged value nor its exchange rate with the US dollar could affect consumer prices, the study was unable to identify any evidence of ERPT to inflation in Nigeria at that time. Nonetheless, it discovered proof of the interest rate pass-through impact.

Razafimahefa (2012) investigated the exchange rate pass-through to domestic pricing and its drivers in sub-Saharan African nations. The investigation discovered an incomplete pass-through. The pass-through is greater after depreciation than after appreciation of the local currency. The average elasticity is predicted to be around 0.4. It is lower in nations with more flexible exchange rates and greater income levels. A low inflation environment, smart monetary policy, and a sustainable fiscal policy are also connected with reduced pass-through rates.

External Sector Division, Research Department of Central Bank (2012) used yearly data for Nigeria from 1980 to 2010 and concluded that the exchange rate pass through was not full in Nigeria since the long- and short-term elasticities were 76.0 % and 31.0 %, respectively. They point out that fluctuations in the exchange rate have raised domestic prices for two straight periods and emphasize the necessity of maintaining exchange rate stability given its significant influence on domestic pricing. However, they discovered that while oil price pass-through was more severe than the ERPT, import price pass-through was quite modest. Adeyemi

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and Samuel (2013) used the VECM technique and data from 1970 to 2008 to examine the ERPT to consumer prices in Nigeria. The findings of their examination of impulse response functions (IRFs) showed that there was a significant ERPT to consumer prices in Nigeria, with a long-term percentage of almost 83%. According to the study, the money supply had less of an impact on Nigeria's growing inflation than the exchange rate.

Adeniji (2013) used Granger-causality and the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) to examine exchange rate volatility and inflation upturn in Nigeria using yearly time series data from 1986 to 2012. The findings of VECM indicate that whereas real GDP has a negative and negligible link with inflation, exchange rate volatility, the money supply, and the budget deficit have a positive and substantial relationship with inflation. Additionally, a bidirectional link between the variables is demonstrated by the Granger causality result. Additionally, Bobai, Ubangida, and Umar (2013) evaluated Nigeria's inflation and exchange rate volatility using yearly time series data from 1986 to 2010. According to the VECM finding, there is a negative shock between inflation and the exchange rate, meaning that as inflation rises, the exchange rate falls.

Jiang and Kim (2013) investigated the effects of exchange rate fluctuations on Chinese producer and retail pricing using the structural VAR technique. According to the study, the pass-through to producer prices was greater than that to retail prices, however ERPT to producer and retail prices were not complete. Alim and Lahiani (2014) examined whether three East Asian and two Latin American nations' exchange rate pass-through is decreased by a credible monetary policy intended to manage inflation. According to their findings, a credible monetary policy regime that tried to manage inflation was linked to reduced ERPT. Additionally, they discovered that Latin American economies had greater ERPT than East Asian ones.

Inam (2015) also conducted an empirical study on Nigerian inflation and exchange rate volatility using yearly data from 1970 to 2011. According to the results of the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression, the exchange rate has a negligible negative impact on the rate of inflation. This suggests that the inflation rate falls when the currency rate declines and vice versa. The Granger-causality test result showed that there was no causal relationship between the two variables in Nigeria. Okoli, Mbah, and Agu (2016) investigated the connection between Nigerian inflation and currency rate volatility. A unidirectional causal relationship between inflation and real exchange rate volatility is demonstrated using the Granger-causality test. This suggests that the economy won't see further inflationary tendencies if the value of the Naira declines.

Bada et al. (2016) studied the aggregate impact of exchange rate pass-through on Nigerian import and consumer prices from 1995Q1 to 2015Q1. The study concluded that the exchange rate pass-through into Nigeria's CPI inflation was insufficient by applying the Johansen technique to cointegration and a vector error correction methodology. The baseline and alternative models' long-term pass-through elasticities were determined to be 0.24 and

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0.30, respectively. It was shown that import prices had a greater influence than consumer prices, suggesting that the pass-through effect diminishes as one moves up the pricing chain.

Obiekwe and Osubuohien (2016) used monthly time series data from 2006:01 to 2015:12 to examine the link between exchange rate volatility and inflation in Nigeria, as well as the extent to which inflation is passed through to the official and parallel currency rates. In the short term, exchange rate volatility and inflation have a negative and significant relationship, according to the Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity (GARCH) and VECM results; in the long term, however, the co-integration result demonstrates a positive and significant relationship between the variables. Additionally, the analysis shows that the official exchange rate only passes through to inflation over the long term, but the parallel exchange rate only passes through to inflation in the near term.

Monfared and Akın (2017) used the Vector Autoregression (VAR) model and the Hendry General to Specific Modeling approach to examine the link between inflation and the exchange rate based on time series data for the years 1976–2012. In order to estimate the VAR model, the study additionally examined quarterly data from 1997Q3 to 2011Q4. The Hendry model produced the conclusion that the exchange rate and inflation are directly related. Inflation increases as foreign currency rates rise. Both the money supply and the exchange rate have a positive impact on inflation when the money supply variable is included in the VAR model.

Gidigbi, Babarinde, and Lawan (2018) looked into how Nigerian price inflation was affected by exchange rate volatility pass-through. Time-series data with annualization from 1981 to 2015. The link between the stated key variables was estimated using the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM). All of the factors included in the model are significant in Granger producing inflation over the long term, according to VECM estimate. There was no short-term correlation between exchange rate volatility and inflation, according to the study. In the short term, however, there was a positive correlation between the money supply and inflation. It is clear from variance decomposition that other important variables or factors in the model have a greater impact on changes in inflation than exchange rate volatility.

Nuhu (2021) studied the impact of exchange rate volatility on inflation in Nigeria using yearly time series data from 1986 to 2019. Using the VECM, his findings revealed that the money supply and nominal exchange rate had a positive and considerable impact on the consumer price index.

Ighoroje and Orife (2022) investigated how Nigeria's inflation rate was impacted by fluctuations in the currency rate. The 1987–2019 deregulated economy period was the focus of the study. Nominal exchange rates were used to depict exchange rate fluctuations, while control variables such as interest rates, money supply, imports, and GDP growth were used to support these claims. Data analysis was done using the OLS and GLS. According to the findings, Nigerian inflation is unaffected by the exchange rate or other macroeconomic factors such as the money supply, interest rates, imports, and GDP. This suggests that Nigeria's inflation rate

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is not primarily caused by macroeconomic factors. Inflation can be caused by social and political factors including political upheaval, consumer confidence, and so on.

Abdullahi (2023) used structural vector auto regression to investigate the influence of macroeconomic shocks on the transmission of exchange rate changes into consumer price inflation. The findings indicate that exchange rate pass-through to consumer price inflation in Nigeria is minimal and partial. Furthermore, the pace of adjustment to structural shocks arising from exchange rate, production, monetary policy rate, and money supply is rapid.

Musandiwa and Ngwakwe (2023) assessed how South Africa's consumer price index was impacted by currency exchange rates. The OLS regression was used to analyze monthly data on exchange rates and the CPI from 2020 to 2021 that were taken from the Fusion Media investment database. Within the parameters of the data, the research demonstrated that exchange rate fluctuations had a large and beneficial impact on CPI. The results have both academic and practical ramifications for comprehending the theoretical short-term period impact of the exchange rate on the consumer price index in the context of South Africa and for the application of advanced economic policies in practice to mitigate potential adverse effects on investment and savings.

Lastly, Jakpa, Ezi, and Egbon (2024) investigated how Nigerian inflation is affected by exchange rate pass-through. The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model was employed as the analytical approach for the 1990–2022 research period. The results show that whereas import prices have a significant and negative impact on consumer prices, exchange rates have a positive and considerable impact on consumer prices. Based on this finding, the study recommended that monetary authorities use caution when devaluing the home currency in an attempt to spur economic expansion, as this would likely raise the ERPT in addition to aggravating domestic inflation. Other recent empirical works are Effiong et al. (2022), and Effiong et al. (2025).

2.4 Summary of Empirical Literature Reviewed

The empirical studies have portrayed divergent findings on the exchange rate pass-through effect with majority of the studies reporting partial and incomplete pass-through effect on inflation (see Aliyu et al., 2008; Bada et al., 2016; Monfared and Akin, 2017; Abdullahi, 2023). Most of the studies have focused on using the VAR and VECM in the analysis to obtain both the short run and long run elasticities for the exchange rate pass-through coefficient. This study therefore applies both the fully modified ordinary least squares (FMOLS) and the VAR model to estimate the exchange rate pass-through elasticities for Nigeria using recent data with higher frequencies. The VAR model aid in obtaining the impulse response function to check how consumer prices respond to innovations in the exchange rate and other key variables in the model such as import prices and crude oil price.

3. METHODOLOGY

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3.1 Model Specification

The model for this study was formulated drawing insights from the work of Ghosh and Rajan (2009) in estimating the exchange rate pass-through for Korea and Thailand, where the consumer price index was expressed as a function of exchange rate, United States producer price index, and output growth. The US Producer Price Index (USPPI) was incorporated in the model to capture how import prices could affect domestic prices within the domestic economy. Thus, exchange rate can pass through the import prices to affect the domestic price level. Hence, such interaction is crucial to be incorporated in the model especially in the case where the VAR model will be incorporated.

The original model is specified as follows:

$$\ln(P^i)_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \ln(E_j^i)_t + \alpha_2 \ln(GDP^i)_t + \alpha_3 \ln(PPI^j)_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

where i denotes Korea or Thailand, j connotes United States or Japan, P^i denotes the import prices or CPI of Korea or Thailand, E_j^i is the exchange rate of Korea and Thailand per dollar or Japanese Yen, PPI denotes the producer price index of the United States or Japan, and GDP denote the gross domestic product of Korea or Thailand. By transforming Equation (1) and incorporating crude oil price due to its significance on the Nigerian economy, the model for this study is therefore specified as follows:

$$CPI_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 EXCR_t + \beta_2 USPPI_t + \beta_3 OILP_t + \beta_4 RGDP_t + \mu_t \quad (2)$$

Where CPI is the consumer price index, EXCH is the exchange rate of the naira per dollar, USPPI is the United States producer price index (a proxy for world import prices), OILP is the global price of Brent Crude (U.S. Dollars per Barrel, Quarterly, Not Seasonally Adjusted), and RGDP is the growth rate of gross domestic product.

3.2 Nature and sources of Data

This study utilized quarterly data from the first quarter of 1995 (1995Q1) to the last quarter of 2023 (2023Q4). The data was obtained for key variables in the model which were consumer price index, exchange rate, United States producer price index, crude oil price, and real GDP growth. These data were obtained strictly from secondary sources. While data on real GDP and exchange rate were obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria (2023) statistical bulletin, data on crude oil price was obtained from the International Monetary Fund (retrieved from the Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis). Also, data on consumer price index and United States producer price index were obtained from Ha et al. (2023) on “global database of inflation” and Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (2025) respectively. These databases are reliable and officially recognized to generate the desired data for this study.

3.3 Technique of Data Analysis

The empirical analysis begins by checking the stationarity property of the time series variables for the study. The test was conducted based on the Augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root test with drift and trend assumption to ascertain the order of integration of the time series

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variables. This was later followed by checking for cointegration using the Hansen parameter instability test for cointegrating relationships. The long run estimates of the model were estimated using the fully modified ordinary least squares (FMOLS) technique of analysis due to the prevailing higher order of integration recorded from the series.

The study further utilized the five-variable VAR model with exchange rates and the two variables of import and consumer prices being the key variables in the analysis, and oil price and real GDP growth being the control variables. The general VAR model is specified as follows:

$$Y_t = \phi_i + \sum_{i=1}^p \delta_i Y_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \quad (3)$$

Where Y_t represents the vectors of the endogenous variables (CPI, EXCR, USPPi, OILP, and RGDP), ϕ_i is a vector of the constants in the VAR system, δ_i denotes a vector of autoregressive estimates, and ε_t is the error term assumed to be white noise. It is worth nothing that the optimal lag for the VAR system is lag 2 ($p = 2$) which was selected based on the optimal lag selection criterion of Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), Schwarz Information Criterion (SIC), and Hannan-Quinn (HQ) criterion. The VAR estimation process will therefore generate the impulse response functions to check how each of the endogenous variables responds to shock arising from other endogenous variables within the VAR system.

The two main factors in the analysis are import and consumer prices, as well as exchange rates. As oil prices rise, more money is received, which might result in the accumulation of reserves and a future appreciation in the value of the naira, which would lower inflation. Increased inflation and exchange rate depreciation are caused by rising import and consumer prices (Bada et al., 2016). As a result, real output and import prices will be positive, while the vector coefficients of the exchange rate variable and crude oil prices will be negative.

4. EMPIRICAL FINDINGS

4.1 Stylized Facts

The trends in the consumer price index (CPI) and the United States' producer price index (USPPI) are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Trends in consumer price index and United States' producer price index

The trend presented in Figure 1 connotes the fact that both the CPI of Nigeria and the USPPI have been moving in the same direction over the years. In the 1980s and early 2000s, the CPI for Nigeria was far below the USPPI. The CPI of Nigeria stood at 21.27 in the first quarter of 1995 and rose steadily to 91.20 in the first quarter of 2008. Within the same period, the USPPI rose from 66.31 to 91.67 respectively. With the CPI rising continuously over the years from 104.37 in 2010Q1 to 228.40 in 2018Q1 with a further increase to 497.59 in 2023Q4, the USPPI was below the CPI as it declined from 108.21 in 2014Q1 to 51.18 in 2020Q. However, the USPPI maintained an upward trend thereafter with some periods of fluctuations to 73.25 in 2021Q1 with a further increase to 82.89 in 2023Q4. This pattern of movements in these two variables portrays some sort of relationship between them over the years.

The trends of CPI and exchange rate (EXCR) is also captured in Figure 2 where the two variables tend to exhibit similar pattern of movements over the years. The two variables maintained an upward trend over the years with exchange rate depicting some sort of fluctuations in some periods therefore exhibiting periods of appreciation and depreciation of the naira relative to the US dollar.

It can be observed that the exchange rate of the naira relative to the dollar maintained a stable value of ₦21.89/\$1 from the first quarter of 1995 to the last quarter of 1998. This was followed by a substantial depreciation of the domestic currency to ₦86.97/\$1 in the first quarter of 1999. This depreciation continued consistently up to ₦132.87/\$1 in 2005Q2 before appreciation set in the third quarter of 2005 where the \$1 exchanged for ₦130.81. This period of appreciation of the naira could not stand the test of time as it only lasted up to 2008Q3 where the exchange rate was ₦117.73/\$1.

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Figure 2: Trends in consumer price index and Exchange rate

Thereafter, the exchange rate depreciated massively to ₦149.83/\$1 in 2010Q1 with no significant appreciation (observable between 2012Q4 and 2014Q3) before the economy was plunged back to period of depreciation to the tune of N169.68/\$1 in 2014Q4. This depreciation continued consistently till 2023 as the exchange rate depreciated from ₦306.40/\$1 in 2017Q1 to ₦381.00/\$1 in 2020Q4 with a further depreciation to ₦899.07/\$1 in 2023Q. As could be observed from Figure 2, both CPI and exchange rate moved in the same direction which portrays the existence of some sort of relationship between them.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

The result presented in Table 1 captures the descriptive properties of the variables utilized for this study.

Table 1: Descriptive properties of the variables

	CPI	EXCR	USPPI	OILP	RGDP
Mean	138.27	188.68	91.91	58.00	6.27
Median	96.35	148.95	92.58	56.12	3.02
Maximum	497.59	899.07	142.19	122.22	28.64
Minimum	21.27	21.89	66.31	11.50	-24.09
Std. Dev.	113.66	147.20	19.55	32.04	47.96
Skewness	1.23	1.90	0.62	0.33	10.02
Kurtosis	3.80	8.27	2.96	1.97	15.60
Jarque-Bera	32.57	204.16	7.48	7.29	52.02
Probability	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.03	0.00
Observations	116	116	116	116	116

Source: Researcher Computation

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The CPI recorded a mean value of 138.27 having a standard deviation of 113.66. The variable has a minimum value and maximum value of 21.27 and 497.59 respectively, and it is positively skewed and leptokurtic in nature. Exchange rate averaged ₦188.68/\$1 during the period under consideration with a standard deviation of 147.20. While the minimum and maximum values were respectively ₦21.89 and ₦899.07/\$1, the variable exhibits a positively skewed and leptokurtic distribution. The USPPPI averaged 91.91 with a maximum and minimum value of 142.19 and 66.31 respectively. With the standard deviation of 19.55, the variable is positively skewed and platykurtic in its distribution. The global oil price during the study period averaged \$58 per barrel (pb) with a maximum and minimum value of \$122.22 pb and \$11.50 pb respectively. While the standard deviation is 32.04, the variable is positively skewed and platykurtic in its distribution. The Nigerian economy recorded an average RGDP growth rate of 6.27% with a standard deviation of 47.96. The variable positively skewed and leptokurtic in nature.

4.3 Correlation Analysis

To check the association between variables in the model, the correlation analysis is conducted based on the Pearson correlation analysis. The result is presented in Table 2 where negative coefficient signifies negative association, and positive sign denotes positive association between the variables concerned.

Table 2: Correlation matrix

	CPI	EXCR	USPPI	OILP	RGDP
CPI	1				
EXCR	0.9545	1			
USPPI	0.9326	0.8625	1		
OILP	0.4740	0.3905	0.7430	1	
RGDP	-0.0288	-0.0168	0.0091	0.0665	1

Source: Researcher Computation

From the result in Table 2, the CPI exhibited strong positive correlation with both exchange rate and USPPI given their correlation coefficient of +0.9545 and +0.9326 respectively. Also, CPI and oil price are positively correlation, but the degree of association is weak given the correlation coefficient of +0.474. However, CPI and RGDP exhibited a weak negative correlation given the coefficient of -0.0288. The regressors do not exhibit any form of perfect linear relationship with each other hence, the possibility of multicollinearity is ruled out. Since correlation does not imply any cause-effect relationship, there is need to further establish such which will be captured using the regression analysis.

4.4 Stationarity Test

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The stationarity test was conducted in order to ascertain the order of integration of the time series variables utilized for the study. The test was conducted based on the Augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root test with constant and trend assumption. It is required that the t-statistic must be negative and statistically significant at the 5% level for the null hypothesis to be rejected. Table 3 presents the result of the test where I(0), I(1) and I(2) denotes that the variable is stationary at level, first difference, and second difference respectively.

Table 3: Unit root test result

Variables	ADF Statistic						Order of Integration
	Level	p-value	First Difference	p-value	Second Difference	p-value	
CPI	5.2315	1.0000	3.1180	1.0000	-10.456	0.0000	I(2)
EXCR	2.1321	1.0000	-3.2079	0.0881	-10.1374	0.0000	I(2)
USPPI	-2.1334	0.5214	-4.4552	0.0027	-----	-----	I(1)
OILP	-2.8312	0.1894	-8.1642	0.0000	-----	-----	I(1)
RGDP	-10.564	0.0000	-----	----	-----	-----	I(0)

Source: Researcher Computation

The unit root test result presented in Table 3 indicates that both CPI and EXCR were stationary at second difference given that their respective ADF statistic became significant upon the variables being differenced twice. Therefore, CPI and EXCR are I(2) time series variables. Also, the USPPI and OILP were stationary at first difference given that their respective ADF statistic became stationary upon first differencing. Thus, both USPPI and OILP are I(1) time series variables. On the contrary, only RGDP was stationary at level hence, it is an I(0) time series variable. Since the variables reported higher order of integration the fully modified ordinary least squares (FMOLS) technique is utilized to derive the parameter estimates.

4.5 Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) Model Estimation

The FMOLS estimation technique was deployed to obtain the parameter estimates of the model since some of the variables were stationary at second difference. Therefore, the cointegration test is first conducted and the result is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Cointegration Test - Hansen Parameter Instability

Series: CPI EXCR USPPI OILP RGDP				
Null hypothesis: Series are cointegrated				
Cointegrating equation deterministic: C				
	Stochastic	Deterministic	Excluded	
Lc statistic	Trends (m)	Trends (k)	Trends (p2)	Probability
0.788481	4	0	0	0.097

Source: Researcher Computation

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The cointegration test result presented in Table 4 based on the Hansen parameter instability test generated Lc statistic of 0.788481 with a p-value of 0.097 which is statistically insignificant at the 5% level of significance. Since the Lc statistic is insignificant, the null hypothesis that the series are cointegrated is therefore accepted. Consequently, there is cointegration in the model and the cointegration regression model is estimated based on the FMOLS which Table 5 presents the result.

Table 5: FMOLS estimates

Dependent Variable: CPI
Method: Fully Modified Least Squares (FMOLS)
Sample (adjusted): 1995Q2 2023Q4
Included observations: 115 after adjustments
Cointegrating equation deterministics: C
Long-run covariance estimate (Bartlett kernel, Newey-West fixed bandwidth = 5.0000

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Probability
EXCR	0.1849	0.0497	3.7174	0.0003
USPPI	5.9876	0.5152	11.6219	0.0000
OILP	-1.4086	0.1734	-8.1213	0.0000
RGDP	-0.0455	0.0522	-0.8723	0.3850
C	-365.5960	30.3748	-12.0362	0.0000
R-squared	0.9822	Mean dependent var		139.2915
Adjusted R-squared	0.9816	S.D. dependent var		113.6218
S.E. of regression	15.4291	Sum squared resid		26186.4000
Long-run variance	714.9219			

Source: Researcher Computation

The regression result presented in Table 5 indicated that exchange rate exerted a positive and significant effect on the consumer price index. This therefore implies that exchange rate depreciation increases inflationary tendencies within the Nigerian economy. Hence, the long run exchange rate pass-through coefficient of 0.1849 is an indication that a 1% increase in exchange rate will lead to a 0.1849% increase in the rate of inflation in the long run. The findings indicate that exchange rate pass-through to consumer price inflation in Nigeria is minimal and partial. This aligns with the earlier findings such as Aliyu et al. (2008), Sahaa and Zhanga (2011), Razafimahefa (2012), Bada et al. (2016), Monfared and Akın (2017) and Abdullahi (2023).

Also, the USPPI exerted a positive and significant long run effect on inflation in Nigeria. Therefore, an increase in the US producer price index will affect Nigeria's domestic prices since Nigeria is an import dependent economy with some of her importation coming from the United States of America. Consequently, a 1% increase in the US producer price index

will lead to a 5.9876% increase in Nigeria’s domestic prices. This clearly portrays that import prices can influence domestic prices through the transfer of such prices to the consumers. Further, oil price exerted a negative and significant effect on inflation in Nigeria. Rising oil prices will lead to a greater increase in the revenue of the government since Nigeria is an oil dependent economy. This will reduce the fiscal deficit which has been pointed out in the literature as a key driver of inflationary pressure. Therefore, a 1% increase in crude oil prices will lead to a 1.4086% decrease in domestic prices. Lastly, real GDP growth exerted a negative but insignificant effect on domestic prices during the period of analysis.

4.6 Vector Autoregression

The vector autoregression was utilized to estimate the exchange rate pass-through effect on inflation in Nigeria. This approach aids in ascertaining the key variable(s) through which exchange rate influences domestic prices. The process begins with the determination of the optimal lag followed by the estimation of the VAR model.

4.6.1 VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria

The VAR model must be estimated using an optimal lag length to be determined using lag selection criteria. Such include the Akaike information criterion (AIC), the Schwarz information criterion (SIC), and Hannan-Quinn (HQ) criterion. The lag length with the lowest AIC, SIC and HQ value yields the optimal lag to be included in the VAR model estimation. The result in Table 6 presents the optimal lag length selection.

Table 6: Lag order selection result

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SIC	HQ
0	-2644.81	NA	2.44e+14	47.31809	47.43946	47.36733
1	-1878.64	1450.254	4.36e+08	34.08288	34.81105	34.37832
2	-1817.07	111.051	2.28e+08*	33.42980*	34.76477*	33.97144*
3	-1799.40	30.28357	2.61e+08	33.56077	35.50256	34.34861
4	-1773.19	42.60363	2.59e+08	33.53903	36.08762	34.57307

* indicates lag order selected by the criterion

LR: sequential modified LR test statistic (each test at 5% level)

FPE: Final prediction error

AIC: Akaike information criterion

SC: Schwarz information criterion

HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion

Source: Researcher Computation

The result presented in Table 6 indicated that at lag 2, we have the lowest AIC, SIC and HQ values. Therefore, the optimal lag to be incorporated in the VAR model estimation is 2 lags.

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4.6.2 Vector Autoregression Model Estimation

To ascertain the exchange rate pass-through effect on inflation in Nigeria, the VAR model is estimated, and the result is presented in Table 7.

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Table 7: Vector Autoregression Estimates

	CPI	EXCR	USPPI	OILP	RGDP
CPI(-1)	1.554153 [17.3203]	2.804129 [3.23755]	0.087704 [0.92646]	-0.481144 [-0.95397]	1.004886 [0.36659]
CPI(-2)	-0.559978 [-6.16852]	-3.000405 [-3.42410]	-0.07397 [-0.77234]	0.424224 [0.83138]	-1.417209 [-0.51104]
EXCR(-1)	0.018875 [1.95601]	1.497869 [16.0814]	-0.016108 [-1.58229]	0.000746 [0.01375]	-0.067034 [-0.22740]
EXCR(-2)	-0.018119 [-1.68887]	-0.584935 [-5.64828]	0.019046 [1.68271]	0.036641 [0.60760]	0.134039 [0.40897]
USPPI(-1)	0.380891 [2.51602]	4.599286 [3.14746]	0.665874 [4.16917]	-1.372063 [-1.61244]	0.005475 [0.00118]
USPPI(-2)	-0.195037 [-1.38762]	-2.726799 [-2.00985]	0.244713 [1.65027]	1.755317 [2.22181]	2.070734 [0.48226]
OILP(-1)	-0.043132 [-1.52461]	-0.825692 [-3.02367]	0.131753 [4.41434]	1.424210 [8.95635]	0.635495 [0.73533]
OILP(-2)	-0.009159 [-0.31338]	0.319037 [1.13093]	-0.118323 [-3.83752]	-0.583463 [-3.55180]	-0.984452 [-1.10265]
RGDP(-1)	-0.002873 [-0.89658]	-0.020917 [-0.67631]	-0.000155 [-0.04583]	-0.003763 [-0.20896]	-0.014428 [-0.14740]
RGDP(-2)	0.002455 [0.76547]	0.000687 [0.02220]	0.000629 [0.18602]	-0.000918 [-0.05091]	0.008245 [0.08416]
C	-11.65403 [-2.39002]	-108.9493 [-2.31476]	5.585087 [1.08568]	-21.69384 [-0.79152]	-123.8375 [-0.83135]
R-squared	0.999812	0.989504	0.992839	0.924458	0.031910
Adj. R-squared	0.999794	0.988485	0.992144	0.917124	-0.06208
Sum sq. resids	274.3105	25558.19	305.3190	8666.590	255992.4
S.E. equation	1.631934	15.75239	1.721703	9.172876	49.85342
F-statistic	54745.87	971.0475	1428.044	126.0477	0.339503
Log likelihood	-211.8085	-470.2723	-217.913	-408.6278	-601.6112
Akaike AIC	3.908922	8.443374	4.016018	7.361892	10.74756
Schwarz SC	4.172941	8.707393	4.280037	7.625911	11.01158
Mean dependent	140.3048	191.6027	92.35465	58.70893	6.361288
S.D. dependent	113.6004	146.7975	19.42453	31.86326	48.37449

Note: t-statistics are enclosed in square brackets [].

Source: Researcher Computation.

The result presented in Table 7 indicates that both the first period lag and the second lag of CPI exerted a significant effect on the current period CPI. This is an indication that CPI

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is strongly endogenous in predicting itself. Thus, the first period lag increased the current CPI by 1.5542% on the average while the second period lag of CPI reduces the current CPI by 0.60% on the average. Consequently, it can be adduced that expectations drives the consumer price index within the Nigerian economy. Further, the one period lag of CPI increased exchange rate by about 2.8041% on the average while the second period lag of CPI reduces exchange rate by 3.0% on the average. Thus, CPI is strongly exogenous in predicting exchange rate variations during the study period. However, CPI is weakly exogenous in predicting the changes in USPPPI, OILP, and RGDP during the study period.

The effect of exchange rate on CPI indicates that the first period lag of exchange rate exerted a positive and significant effect on CPI while the second period lag exerted a negative effect. Therefore, the exchange rate pass-through effect on inflation varies over time. Thus, the previous year's exchange rate increases the current year's CPI by 0.0189% on the average while the past two year's exchange rate reduces the current CPI by about 0.0181% on the average. This portrays that exchange rate is strongly exogenous in predicting the variations in CPI in Nigeria. Also, exchange rate is strongly endogenous in predicting itself given that the first period and the second period lags of exchange rate exerted a significant effect on the current period's exchange rate. From the estimated coefficient, the previous year's exchange rate increased the current period's exchange rate by 1.4979% on the average while the second period lag reduces the current period's exchange rate by 0.5849% on the average. Exchange rate was also noted to be strongly exogenous in predicting USPPPI. In the first period lag, exchange rate exerted a negative and significant effect on USPPPI by reducing it by 0.016% on the average. However, the second period lag of exchange rate reduced the current USPPPI by about 0.019% on the average. It was further noted that exchange rate was weakly exogenous in predicting OILP and RGDP during the study period.

The effect of USPPPI on CPI in the first period was positive and significant while the effect became negative but insignificant in the second period. Thus, the USPPPI increased the CPI by about 0.38% on the average. Hence, the USPPPI is strongly exogenous on predicting CPI within the Nigerian economy. Given this notable transmission, it can be adduced that the exchange rate pass through the USPPPI to affect the domestic prices within the Nigerian economy. The estimated model further portrayed that the USPPPI exerted a significant effect on the exchange rate which presents a feedback mechanism within the system. From the estimated coefficient, the previous year's USPPPI increased the current period exchange rate by about 4.5992% on the average while its second period lag reduced exchange rate by about 2.7268% on the average. As a result, USPPPI is strongly exogenous in predicting exchange rate in Nigeria. The USPPPI was strongly endogenous in predicting itself since its lags exerted a significant effect. Thus, the first period and second period lags of USPPPI increased the current USPPPI by 0.6659% and 0.24471% respectively. The USPPPI was also strongly exogenous in predicting crude oil prices during the study period. The estimated coefficient indicated that the one period lag of USPPPI reduced the crude oil price by 1.372% on the average while the second period lag

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of USPPPI increased the current crude oil prices by 1.7553% on the average. However, USPPPI was weakly exogenous in predicting RGDP during the study period.

The result further portrayed that oil price only exerted a significant effect on CPI at the one period lag while the effect was insignificant with the second lag. Thus, the first period lag of crude oil price reduced the CPI by about 0.0431% on the average hence, oil price is strongly exogenous in predicting consumer price index in Nigeria. The oil price was also strongly exogenous in predicting exchange rate and the USPPPI. The first period lag of crude oil price caused the exchange rate to reduce by 0.8257% on the average. On the contrary, the first period lag of crude oil price increased the USPPPI by 0.1318% on the average while its second period lag reduced the USPPPI by 0.1183% on the average. This result therefore establishes a feedback effect between USPPPI and crude oil price during the period of analysis. The crude oil price was strongly exogenous in predicting itself during the study period. The first period lag of crude oil price increased the current period crude oil price by 1.4242% while its second period lag reduced the current crude oil price by 0.5835% on the average. Crude oil price was further observed to be weakly exogenous in predicting RGDP during the study period.

For RGDP, the VAR estimates portrayed that it was weakly endogenous in predicting itself as well as being weakly exogenous in predicting CPI, exchange rate, and USPPPI. The estimated VAR model further portrayed that CPI would assume a negative value of -11.65 if all the regressors are held constant. Also, exchange rate will assume a negative value of -108.95 if all the explanatory variables were held constant. The value of USPPPI, OILP, and RGDP would assume a value of zero since their intercepts were statistically insignificant. The R-squared indicated that the explanatory variables in model explained 99.98% of the total variations in CPI; 98.95% of the total variation in exchange rate; 99.28% of the total variation in USPPPI; 92.45% of the total variations in crude oil price; and just 3.19% of the total variations in output growth (RGDP). The overall models were statistically significant given the significance of their respective F-statistics at the 5% level.

4.7 Impulse Response Function

The impulse response was generated from the VAR framework to depict how shocks in the exogenous variables could affect the consumer price index. Such responses to shocks within the system is presented in Figure 3. It was observed that the CPI responded positively to shocks in exchange rate up to the sixth period after which the response became negative. This portrays the fact that short run spikes in exchange rate could drive price gyrations within the Nigerian economy in the short term. After due adjustments, the positive response is decomposed such that the effect becomes negative over time. The CPI was also observed to respond positively to shocks in the USPPPI up to the 10th period. This is an indication that increased USPPPI will increase the import cost which translates to higher prices of imported goods within the economy. In an attempt for businesspersons to be able to afford foreign goods, the prices of domestic goods are also inflated thereby leading to a concurrent increase in the CPI within the

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Nigerian economy. The CPI was also observed to respond negatively to shocks in crude oil prices up to the 10th period. Thus, positive innovations/shocks in crude oil prices will cause the CPI to decline substantially over time.

Figure 3: Response to Cholesky one SD (d.f. adjusted) innovations ± 2 standard deviation

The impulse response function captured in Figure 3 further indicated that exchange rate responded positively to shocks in USPPi. This implies that any positive innovations in the import prices will cause the exchange rate to rise substantially over time. However, exchange rate responded negatively to shocks in crude oil prices. Thus, any positive innovations in the crude oil prices will lead to an appreciation of the naira relative to the dollar. Meanwhile, the import prices responded negatively to shocks in exchange rate up to the fifth period after which such responses became positive. Finally, the import prices responded positively to shocks in crude oil prices implying that positive innovations in the crude oil market will lead to an increase in the import prices up to the 9th period before the impact is being decomposed. The

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impulse response function therefore portrays a sort of interaction among consumer price index, exchange rate, and United States producer price index with shocks in the real GDP not exerting any significant response from the variables within the system.

4.8 Discussion of Major Findings

The exchange rate pass-through effect in this study have been established to be incomplete given the low coefficient of 0.1849 being estimated. The pass-through has been established to be from exchange rate to import prices to influence the domestic prices. High import prices in an import dependent economy like Nigeria will certainly diffuse to affect domestic prices in terms of cost of core inputs and consumables. The incomplete exchange rate pass-through effect is an indication that exchange rate does not directly affect the domestic prices, but passes through the import prices to affect domestic prices.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The exchange rate pass-through effect on inflation in Nigeria have been examined in this study with the use of quarterly data from 1995Q1 to 2023Q4 making a total of 116 observations. The data for the study was obtained from secondary sources including the Central Bank of Nigeria, Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development, the Global database on inflation, and the Federal Reserve Bank of St Louis. The methodology of the study follows the VAR framework which facilitated the detection of the exchange rate pass-through effect as well as the impulse response function to ascertain how consumer prices responded to shocks in exchange rate, crude oil price, United States producer price index, and the real GDP. The fully modified ordinary least squares (FMOLS) technique was also utilized to estimate the long run parameter estimates for the model given the higher order of integration established by the unit root test.

The result from the FMOLS estimation indicated that exchange rate exerted a positive and significant effect on domestic prices. This therefore is an indication that depreciation of the currency could put forward an upward trend in the domestic price level especially in an import dependent economy like Nigeria. The long run exchange rate pass through coefficient which was 0.1849 is an indication that the domestic consumer price level will increase by 0.1849% is the exchange depreciates by 1% on the average. Further, the United States producer price index also exerted a positive and significant effect on domestic price level indicating that higher production price index in America which is a core trading partner with Nigeria will definitely diffuses into the domestic economy to affect the price level due to trade relationship (a clear case of imported inflation). A 1% increase in the USPPPI will therefore cause the domestic consumer prices to increase by about 5.9876% on the average. This established relationship portrays the interdependence of the domestic consumer prices with trading partner's production price index. The crude oil price was also observed to exert a negative and

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significant effect on domestic prices. This therefore implies that an increase in crude oil prices will reduce domestic prices in the domestic economy.

The VAR estimation result has indicated evidence of the exchange rate pass-through effect on inflation in Nigeria. It was observed that exchange rate there is a feedback mechanism between exchange rate and the domestic price level as the lags of both variables significantly affected each other. In both cases, first period lag of CPI positively affected exchange rate and the first period lag of exchange rate also positively affected the CPI significantly. The exchange rate pass-through coefficient being 0.0189 is an indication that exchange rate depreciation will cause the domestic prices to increase by about 0.0189% on the average. The findings indicate that exchange rate pass-through to consumer price inflation in Nigeria is minimal and partial. However, an increase in CPI will lead to a 2.8041% increase in exchange rate (exchange rate depreciation). The VAR estimates also indicated that exchange rate positively affected the US producer price index and the producer price index in turn positively affected the consumer prices. This therefore implies that exchange rate passes through the US producer price index to affect Nigeria's consumer prices since Nigeria is an export dependent economy. The impulse response function portrayed that the CPI responded positively to innovations in US producer price index and negatively to shocks in crude oil prices. Further, the CPI responded positively to shocks in exchange rate up to the 6th period after which such shocks are decomposed.

This paper therefore concluded that the exchange rate pass-through effect on inflation in Nigeria occurs through the impact of import prices on the domestic price level due to import dependency. It is therefore recommendation that over reliance on import has made the Nigerian economy susceptible to the exchange rate pass-through effect which has been noted to be significant in terms of import prices (as observed from the US producer price index). The Federal Government of Nigeria in conjunction with the National Planning Commission should prioritize structural reforms through the strategic implementation of import substitution policies. By increasing domestic production capacity, Nigeria can reduce dependency on imports, curbing imported inflation.

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